

The Principle of Least Variation and Cosmological Flatness

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Abstract:

By using the new framework of the 8-theory and the principle of least variation Given by the coupling constant equation, a cosmological prediction regarding the Flatness of the matrix is made. The new framework is predicting that the Lorentz Manifold $s = (M, g)$ is becoming more flat with the continuation of time. Reader Is assumed to be familiar with the 8-theory thesis, by the author of this paper.

Introduction

In the 8-theory a varying Lorentz manifold is the entity of description. The Lorentz manifold Is inserted to an Euler Lagrange equation and by doing so, the main equation Of the framework is obtained.

$$s = (M, g) \quad (0)$$

$$L = (s, s', t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial g'^2}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{\partial g'^2}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Are the conditions which the framework is demanding to retain a stationary manifold. Those two conditions describe a time invariant acceleration directed from extrunum Areas of curvature on the Lorenztion manifold. Intersection with the so called dark energy. In addition, if no data is attainable from the first three term, its vividly clear that there is An agreement with Einstein equivalence principle:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial g'^2}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

The coupling constant equation was obtained by demanding a stationary manifold to Experience net variation, $N(V) = 2\left(V + \frac{1}{2}\right)$; $V \geq 0$; $N(V) \in P$ as P to be is the set of Primes and the number one. Those ideas yielded an infinite series, in which each distinct Boson has a distinct Boson matching its $N(V)$ value. Even amount of variations vanish, $2V = 0$.

$$F \quad F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (6)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (7)$$

$$N_V = 2\left(V + \frac{1}{2}\right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (9)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (10)$$

The framework regard (6) as the second main construction of the theory and currently Has five representation and different uses of the equation. (4) Represent the concept of Least variation, the most significant interactions in nature, are those with the largest

Value of total to net $\frac{N(V)}{T(V)}$. By analyzing the ratios of the first elements in the series we

Conclude the ratio $\frac{N(V)}{T(V)} \rightarrow 0$ as $N(V) \rightarrow \infty$, the result is following ratios:

$$\frac{1}{9} = 0.111, \quad \frac{3}{30} = 0.1, \quad \frac{5}{128} = 0.039 \dots$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \quad (9)$$

The biggest ratios are those with the least $N(V)$ amount and thus they are the Most noticeable on the manifold. The third representation of (4) revolves around To the arrow of time. The direction of the series is assumed to match the direction of Time.

So as we increment the time $t(1) = t(1) + \Delta t$ and as we allow the time to aspire Infinity $t \rightarrow \infty$, the manifold will experience higher number of net variations $N(V)$

And the same time the ratio of $\frac{N(V)}{T(V)} \rightarrow 0$, which means that the matric on the manifold Is getting more and more flat. The most curved, or intense interaction than is the first, the Strong interaction due to its largest value of $\frac{N(V)}{T(V)}$.

Using the coupling constant equation (4) it becomes vividly clear that gravitation will Be aspiring to flatness, and the among of curvature of the matric due to the $N(V) \in Gravity$ To the almost not noticeable. It is also possible to derive that the manifold will become more Flat followed by the direction of the arrow. Flatness than, in the 8-theory is a continuous process.

References

[1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)